

DIFFICULTIES IN TRANSLATING MEDICAL TEXTS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK AND RUSSIAN AND PARONYMS IN THEM

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola tibbiy matnlarda paronimlarning tarjimasini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan ilmiy nashrlarning sharhini taqdim etadi. Unda tibbiy nutqda paronimlardan foydalanishda duch keladigan asosiy lingvistik va kognitiv qiyinchiliklar o'rganiladi, odatiy xatolar tahlil qilinadi va tarjima aniqligini oshirish strategiyalari taklif qilinadi. Misollar farmatsevtika bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar, klinik hujjatlar va ingliz tilidagi tibbiy adabiyotlardan olingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *soxta do'stlar, tibbiy nutq, tarjima qiyinchiliklari, tibbiy terminologiya, paronimlar.*

Abstract: *This article presents a review of scientific publications devoted to the study of the specific features of translating paronyms in medical texts. This paper examines the main linguistic and cognitive difficulties caused by paronyms in medical discourse, analyzes typical errors, and suggests strategies to improve translation accuracy. Examples are taken from pharmaceutical manuals, clinical documentation, and medical literature written in English.*

Keywords: *false friends, medical discourse, translation challenges, medical terminology, paronyms.*

Translation is known to be a complex and multifaceted form of linguistic activity. Medical translation, as well as translation of medical and pharmaceutical topics, as noted by M. V. Shirinyan and S. V. Shustova, is a highly specialized type of translation, requiring a translator proficient not only in the relevant foreign language, but also in the specialized terminology of the text being translated [9, p. 298].

I. V. Belyaeva points out that medical translation has a number of lexical, grammatical, and syntactic features that make it unique [3, p. 203]. A review of publications shows that translation scholars identify several key issues in translating medical texts. *For example*, Canadian linguist M. Rouleau identified the following key issues using English and French as examples: 1) features of usage ("private" norms that differ from the norm of the literary language), including the metonymic use of terms and the preferred use of certain parts of speech; 2) variability of terminology; 3) terminological synonymy; 4) problems of translating eponyms; 5) mismatch of affixes in words of common origin; 6) insufficient quality of specialized bi- and multilingual dictionaries. H. Li-Yanke, Doctor of Sciences, Professor, Honorary President of the Permanent International Council of Institutes and Faculties of Translation, proposed a

classification of the difficulties of medical translation applicable to any pairs of languages: 1) terminological problems; 2) difficulties in translating abbreviations; 3) difficulties in translating eponyms; 4) the admissibility of using Anglicisms; 5) features of the compatibility of linguistic units and the structure of the text [9, pp. 298-299].

Paronyms in medicine often stem from Greek or Latin roots. Their morphological similarity can be misleading even for experienced translators. Consider the following English examples:

Paronym Pair	Meaning	Common Translation Error
<i>Aural / Oral</i>	Related to the ear / Related to the mouth	Confusing ear and mouth instructions (e.g., “oral drops” vs. “aural drops”)
<i>Intoxication / Infection</i>	Poisoning / Pathogenic contamination	Misinterpreting “alcohol intoxication” as “infection”
<i>Absorption / Adsorption</i>	Uptake of substance / Surface adhesion	Mixing physical and biological processes
<i>Hypotension / Hypertension</i>	Low blood pressure / High blood pressure	Incorrect use can lead to opposite meaning

Such confusion is especially critical in clinical or pharmaceutical contexts, where even a minor semantic error can alter medical outcomes.

At the same time, as researchers point out, one of the pressing issues of foreign language activity is translation, translation theory and the study of such a complex and vulnerable category for a translator as interlingual paronyms [7, p. 77]

It should be noted that in linguistics, the term "paronym" is traditionally used in both a broad and a narrow sense: in the first sense, paronyms generally refer to any words that are similar in sound, while in the second, they refer only to semantically similar words with the same root [5, p. 47]. Terminological paronymy is understood as “an unintentional merging of similar, but not identical in sound, terminological units that have independent content and form ” [4, p. 28]. The phenomenon of paronymy in speech consists in the fact that the use of consonant pairs in oral or written speech leads to the emergence of unwanted errors, and in the study of foreign languages, it is "destructive in nature," since it interferes with the accurate acquisition of the vocabulary of the target language [1, p. 114].

As O. P. Antipina notes, existing dictionaries of paronyms confirm that paronymic units represent a very broad class in the linguistic system. This raises the question of classifying and organizing a large number of lexical units [2, pp. 13-14].

The most popular typology in linguistics is based on semantic features, which includes three classes of paronyms:

1) Complete paronyms are absolute paronyms, similar in spelling and pronunciation, with stress on the same syllable, but expressing different semantic concepts;

2) Incomplete paronyms are paronyms that relate to the same field, have similar spelling and pronunciation, but in which there is an incomplete division of meaning, causing them to be converged;

3) Synonymous paronyms are paronyms similar in spelling and pronunciation and having the same meaning [6, p. 176].

Let us cite examples of paronymous words in medical terminology, presented in the study of N. E. Khasanova.⁷

1. Medicinal [mə'dɪsɪnəl/ /mə'dɪsɪn] / **Medical** ['mɛ.dɪ.kəl] (Tibbiy / Tibbiy (shifobaxsh / tibbiy; (целебный / медицинский). These paronyms share the same root, but the words themselves have completely different meanings; they are classified as incomplete paronyms.

2. Nephritis [nɪ'frɑɪtɪs/. /nɪ'frɑɪtɪs] / **Neuritis** [njʊə'raɪtɪs] (Nefrit / Nevrit; Нефрит

/ Неврит). These paronyms are coincidental, have a similar root, and are stressed in

the same way, but the meanings are different; they are classified as absolute paronyms.

3. Ureter [jʊə'ri:tər] / **Urethra** [jʊə'ri:θrə] (siydik yo'li / siydik chiqarish kanali ;

мочеточник / мочеиспускательный канал). Both of these words are derived from

the same root but have different meanings; they are considered partial paronyms.

4. Infectious [ɪn'fɛk.ʃəs] / **Infective** [ɪn'fɛk.tɪv] (yuqumli / yuqumli; инфекционный / заразный). This is an example of partial paronyms that share the same root; the semantic meanings of the words differ, but not significantly: the first reflects the cause of the disease (the penetration of an infection—bacteria or virus—into the body), while the second conveys the degree of contagiousness—the disease is transmitted from person to person through contact.

5. Corpus ['kɔ:.pəs] / **Corpse** [kɔ:ps] - a dead body (korpuz / jasad; корпус / труп). These are absolute paronyms.

6. Surgeon ['sɜ:.dʒən] / **Sergeant** ['sɑ:.dʒənt] (jarroh / serjant; хирург / сержант). These are absolute root paronyms, having a purely coincidental similarity.

⁷Khasanova N. E. Paronyms in medical texts and difficulties of their translation. Baltic Institute of Foreign Languages. 2016. 68 p.

7. Bill / Pill (Hisob-Kitob / Tabletkа ;Счет / Пиллюля). These are absolute root paronyms, having a purely coincidental similarity.

8. Laboratory [lə'brɪ.ə.tər.i] / **Ambulatory** [,æm.bjə'leɪ.tər.i]. Laboratoriya / Ambulatoriya (Tibbiy muassasa, bemorlar qatnab davolanadigan joy); Лаборатория / Амбулатория). These are absolute root paronyms, with a purely coincidental similarity.

9. Injection [ɪn'dʒek.ʃən] / **Infection** [ɪn'fek.ʃən]. (In'ektsiya / Infektsiya; Инъекция / Инфекция). These are absolute root paronyms, with a purely coincidental similarity.

Thus, a review of scientific publications devoted to the study of the translation of paronyms in medical texts allows us to draw the following conclusions. Paronyms are a mono- and bilingual phenomenon. Mixing and misusing paronyms in medical practice not only causes misunderstandings and problems for medical professionals in related fields but can also lead to errors in the selection of treatment methods, which is unacceptable. Clearly distinguishing between paronyms is an important requirement for the translation of medical texts. There is a need to compile specialized linguistic reference books on the use of paronyms.

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